

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	--	--

Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform

Md. Anowar Hossain

Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023

(engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Profile of Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Keywords

Crime in higher education, quality enhancement in higher education, international platform, peace of mankind

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	--	--

Table 1, Services for Higher Education in General

Specialized Review Service	Cost for Six Months
Crime Analysis for Higher Education & Reporting for Quality Enhancement	80000USD
Quality Analysis for Higher Education & Reporting for Quality Enhancement	80000USD
Specialized quality review for public & private universities	80000USD
Specialized quality review for a Department of University	80000USD
Compliance Review of Higher Education	80000USD

NB: An additional cost will be added for national & international travel & accommodation

Process for Review

A written application to Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain through e-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com

References

- Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>
- Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01.
<http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>
- Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1-12.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>

Hossain, A., Islam, A. S., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from *Swietenia macrophylla* and *Musa Acuminata* as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent. *Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 3(2), 1-8.

<https://crimsonpublishers.com/tteft/fulltext/TTEFT.000558.php>

Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. (2019). Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers. *Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering*, 4(4).

<https://doi.org/10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650>

Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online)*, USA.

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>;
<https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>

Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., Bhaumik, N. S., Vankar, P. S., & Shukla, D. (2018). Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distilled Organic Extraction of Organic *Tectona grandis* and *Azadirachta indica* with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 2018(1), 1-12.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245102>

Hossain, A., Sun, D., & Samanta, A. (2019). Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. *JResLit Journal of Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15079.62880>

Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>

Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology*, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh* (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>;
- Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29667.94247>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241586>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Engineering of Textile Coloration* City University, Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh].
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854575>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11281.40801>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010c). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer*, ISBN-978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010d). *Principle of garments production*, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010e). *Production monitoring techniques of a knit composite industry*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854541>
- Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844956>
- Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments* [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India.]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854437>
- Hossain, M. A. (2019a). Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 8(89).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11724.18561>; <http://www.ijsei.com/archive-88919.htm>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242756>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	--	--

- Hossain, M. A. (2019b). Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(4).
<https://doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2019c). Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn. *South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(2).
<https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.36346/sarjet.2019.v01i02.002>
- Hossain, M. A. (2020). My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>,
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47. <https://doi.org/10.12691/materials-9-1-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2021b, May 2023). Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination. Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95699>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370.
<https://doi.org/10.14429/dsj.72.17731>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022b, May 2023). Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background. Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia;

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>.

Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square*

<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 1-16.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Md. Anowar Hossain*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8196696>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2549022/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29805.15844>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936097>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936303>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Anowar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25788.21120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240631>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	--	--

- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240342>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12923.49448>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15879.16801>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19654.04160>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35625.16486>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16822.88641>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	--	--

Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>

Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>

Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>

Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27465.93280>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240547>

Hossain, M. A. (2023r). *Anowar's Handbook on Industrial Economics*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34176.81925>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240589>

Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Anowar's Handbook on Machine Technology & Maintenance of Wet Processing Machineries*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22432.76802>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240660>

Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14883.02082>

Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Anowar's Handbook on Microprocessor, Robotics and Control Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26627.07204>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	--	--

- Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17714.17602>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19391.89763>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241043>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Physics (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17294.74561>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241105>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Project Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35461.32480>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing & Quality Control (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23166.77121>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241394>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ab). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327>;
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241183>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *Anwar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*.

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick,
Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,
Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Anwar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-2)*.

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick,
Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,
Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29857.99683>

Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or
right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV),
publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University,*

*Dhaka, Bangladesh; supported by the act of University Grants Commission of
Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-
Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds. Global Summit on
Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>, Rome, Italy.

Hossain, M. A. (2023ah). Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-
Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds. 5th Edition of
International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March
2023; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>, Valencia, Spain.

Hossain, M. A. (2023ai). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating
illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066,
Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056,
Australia, 2022].* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aj). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating
illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of*

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Md. Anwar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021].
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>
Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2686707/v1>
Hossain, M. A. (2023al). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>
Hossain, M. A. (2023am). Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* 1-18.
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>
Hossain, M. A. (2023an). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>
Hossain, M. A. (2023ao). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when self-studying of student/researcher is an automatic contribution for national and worldwide development without getting money. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2831203/v1>
Hossain, M. A. (2023ap). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112431>
Hossain, M. A. (2023aq). First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks. In: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056,
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>.
Hossain, M. A. (2023ar). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind*. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Industry, enr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Hossain, M. A. (2023as). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Polymer Science & Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31974.80969>

Hossain, M. A. (2023at). Md. Anowar Hossain, Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>.

Hossain, M. A. (2023au). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on "camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds"* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>

Hossain, M. A. (2023av). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966475>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aw). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933678>,

Hossain, M. A. (2023ax). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933704>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ay). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>;

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023be). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bh, 10-11 July 2023). An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm. Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>, Paris, France.
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bi). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, “Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world”

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	--	--

for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.

- <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>
Hossain, M. A. (2023bj). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds*, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>
Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). *Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8196694>
Hossain, M. A. (2023). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain as per office order of RMIT University, Australia*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8273064>
Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>
Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. .

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8194679>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182530>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bo). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182709>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8273582>

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023bq). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

Hossain, M. A. (2023br). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions. *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). UV-Visible-NIR Camouflage Textiles with Natural Plant Based Natural Dyes on Natural Fibre against Woodland Combat Background for Defence Protection. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square, 1-20*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2126958/v1>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
---	---	--

Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection.

Scientific Reports. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anwar Hossain (Part-01)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anwar Hossain (Part-02)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A., Abser, M. N., & Samanta, A. K. Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent, submitted for publication. .

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>

Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 8(5), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>

Md. Anwar Hossain, A. K. S. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240.

<https://doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Md. Anwar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
---	--	--

Samanta, A. K., Hossain, A., Bagchi, A., & Bhattacharya, K. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications*, 2(4), 25-34. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16757.35048>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, **Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform**, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Md. Anowar Hossain, "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world"